

Common Circumstances Before Suicide Involving Firearms Among Black American Adults: Understanding the Challenges and How We Can Help

Most suicide deaths involve firearms, and firearms are the deadliest method of suicide.¹ **Rates of suicide using firearms have been rising among Black American adults.**²

We must understand the challenges people face before these tragedies happen. This study summarized the personal challenges Black American adults often experience before dying by firearm suicide.³

Knowing the challenges Black Americans experience can help save lives in our community. But this is not enough. We must also understand suicide warning signs and work towards prevention.

Scan the following QR code for more information about:

- **Warning signs.** Suicide warning signs include talking about, planning (such as random goodbye texts, calls, notes, and giving away sentimental items), or researching ways to die.
- **Safe firearm storage.** Creating space and time between a firearm and someone having suicidal thoughts can help save a life.⁴
- **Resources.** National suicide prevention and mental health resources.

The following circumstances might occur in combination:

WORSENING MENTAL OR PHYSICAL HEALTH

Increased symptoms in mental or physical health conditions. Mental health conditions might include depression and anxiety. Physical health conditions might include pain, cancer, and chronic illnesses (like diabetes).

Individuals who have health conditions might stop treatment before suicide.

RELATIONSHIP PROBLEMS & FREQUENT ARGUMENTS WITH LOVED ONES

Worsening romantic relationships due to infidelity or breakup, causing anger, sorrow, and grief.

Intense arguments might be common before a suicide attempt.

ALCOHOL AND SUBSTANCE USE

Alcohol and other substances might be used before a suicide attempt to help cope with stresses of life.

FINANCIAL AND LEGAL DIFFICULTIES

Recent job loss, not being hired for a job, or needing to work multiple jobs to make ends meet.

Cannot pay mortgage or rent, experiencing homelessness, losing a vehicle, or owing money.

Legal difficulties such as court hearings or previous arrests, often with financial difficulties.

ACCESSIBLE FIREARMS

Different types of firearms might be purchased legally or illegally before suicide. Firearms might be stolen or borrowed from friends, romantic partners, or family members before suicide. Handguns are very common.

Firearms might be unsafely stored or unlocked in the home. But safe firearm storage is still common before suicide (like using a gun safe or lock).

When someone is experiencing suicidal thoughts, it might be difficult to voluntarily limit their firearm access because they may want to keep their firearms close for protection or their constitutional right to bear arms.

Dial 9-8-8 at any time if you or a loved one is thinking about suicide or experiencing a crisis.

The 9-8-8 Suicide & Crisis Lifeline is available 24/7 to offer free and confidential support.